

TARNAS G4 Grammar

In the following, we present the ANTLR4 (<https://www.antlr.org/>) G4 grammar used by TARNAS to generate parsers for BPSEQ, CT, DB, AAS, and FASTA formats. RNAML is managed through the W3C Document Object Model (DOM) API Reference documentation (<https://www.w3.org/TR/DOM-Level-3-Core/>).

```
grammar RNASecondaryStructure;

@header{
package it.unicam.cs.bdslab.tarnas.model.antlr;
}

// Grammar rules
rna_format: aas | ct | edbn | bpseq | fasta | rnaml ;
aas: COMMENT* sequence? bonds+ ;
edbn: COMMENT* sequence? edbn_structure ;
fasta: COMMENT* sequence ;
bpseq: (BPSEQCTLINES? | COMMENT*) bpseq_structure ;
ct: (BPSEQCTLINES? | COMMENT*) LINECT ct_structure ;
edbn_structure: EDBN+ ;
sequence: NUCLEOTIDE+ ;
bonds: BOND SEP? ;
ct_structure: ct_line+ ;
ct_line: INDEX NUCLEOTIDE (ZERO_INDEX | INDEX) (ZERO_INDEX | INDEX)
ZERO_INDEX INDEX #ctLineUnpaired
        | INDEX NUCLEOTIDE (ZERO_INDEX | INDEX) (ZERO_INDEX | INDEX)
INDEX INDEX #ctLineBond ;
bpseq_structure: bpseq_line+ ;
bpseq_line: INDEX NUCLEOTIDE ZERO_INDEX #bpseqLineUnpaired | INDEX
NUCLEOTIDE INDEX #bpseqLineBond ;
rnaml: XML_HEADER_LINE1 XML_HEADER_LINE2 XML_CONTENT #rnamlContent ;

// Lexer tokens
INDEX: [1-9] [0-9]* ;
ZERO_INDEX: '0' ;
SEP: ',' | ';' ;
BOND: '(' INDEX SEP INDEX ')' ;
BPSEQCTLINES: LINE1BPSEQCT LINE2BPSEQCT LINE3BPSEQCT LINE4BPSEQCT ;
```

```

LINECT: NONEWLINE*? ( 'ENERGY' | 'Energy' | 'dG' ) .*? '\r'? '\n' ;
fragment NONEWLINE: ~( '\r' | '\n' ) ;
fragment IUPAC_CODE: [ACGUacguTtRrYysSWwKkMmBbDdHhVvNn-] ;
NUCLEOTIDE: ( IUPAC_CODE | NON_STANDARD_CODE )+ ;
fragment NON_STANDARD_CODE: '"' | '?' | '[' | '~' | '[' | '_' | '+'
| '=' | '/' | '4' | '7' | 'P' | 'O' | 'I' ;
fragment EDBN_CODE: '.' | '(' | ')' | '[' | ']' | '{' | '}' | '<' |
'>' | [a-zA-Z] ;
EDBN: EDBN_CODE+ ;
LINE1BPSEQCT: 'Filename' .*? '\r'? '\n' ;
LINE2BPSEQCT: 'Organism' .*? '\r'? '\n' ;
LINE3BPSEQCT: 'Accession' .*? '\r'? '\n' ;
LINE4BPSEQCT: 'Citation' .*? '\r'? '\n' ;
XML_HEADER_LINE1: '<?xml' .*? '?' '\r'? '\n' ;
XML_HEADER_LINE2: '<!DOCTYPE rnaml SYSTEM "rnaml.dtd">' '\r'? '\n' ;
XML_CONTENT: '<rnaml' .*? '>' .*? '</rnaml>' ;
COMMENT: ('#' | '>') .*? '\r'? '\n' ;
WS: [ \t\r\n]+ -> skip ; // skip spaces, tabs, newlines

```